

Sleep Duration and Its Correlation with Hypertension Among College Students in West Bengal: Findings from a Cross-Sectional Study

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Abstract—This study investigates the relationship between sleep duration and hypertension among 201 college students aged 17-20 years in West Bengal. A structured interview schedule was utilized to collect data on the participants' sleep patterns and hypertension status. The relationship between sleep duration and hypertension was analyzed using binary logistic regression analysis. The results of the analysis indicate no significant association between sleep duration and hypertension, demonstrating that sleep duration is not a risk factor for hypertension in young adults. These findings suggest that other factors may contribute more significantly to the development of hypertension in this demographic.

Keywords— Sleep duration, Hypertension, College students, young adults, Risk factors.

1. INTRODUCTION

Hypertension, also known as high blood pressure, is a chronic medical disorder characterized by increased pressure in the arteries. It is a non-communicable disease (NCD) that affects about 20% of the population in most communities of all ages and backgrounds (WHO, 1996). Hypertension is often referred to as a "silent killer" because it typically does not cause noticeable symptoms in its early stages, but it can lead to severe complications if left untreated (Dzau & Balatbat, 2019). Blood pressure is a measurement of the force exerted by blood against the artery walls as the heart circulates it throughout the body. It is recorded as two numbers: systolic pressure over diastolic pressure, measured in millimeters of mercury (mmHg).

As per the classification of The Seventh Report of the Joint National Committee on Prevention, Detection, Evaluation, and Treatment of High Blood Pressure (JNC 7, 2003), normal blood pressure is typically around or less than 120/80 mmHg. Hypertension is defined as when blood pressure consistently measures 140/90 mmHg or higher. However, the specific thresholds for diagnosis and treatment may vary depending on individual factors and medical guidelines.

According to Pan American Health Organization (PAHO) in association with WHO (HEARTS in the Americas on World Hypertension Day, 2020.), hypertension affects more than 30% of the adult population worldwide, more than one billion people around the world. The burden of high blood pressure is felt disproportionately in low- and middle-earnings countries, wherein two thirds of cases are found, largely due to increased risk factors in those populations in recent decades (WHO, 2020). The primary threats associated with hypertension (Health Threats from High Blood Pressure, 2022) are - cardiovascular diseases such as heart attack, heart failure, stroke, and peripheral artery disease. High blood pressure can damage the blood vessels in the kidneys, affecting their ability to filter waste products and regulate fluid balance in the body. It can also damage the blood vessels in the eyes, leading to retinopathy, a condition that can cause vision loss or even blindness. Hypertension is often associated with metabolic syndrome, which includes high blood sugar, abnormal cholesterol levels, and excess abdominal fat.

The prevalence of hypertension varies with area and country socioeconomic level. According to the World Health Organization (WHO, 2023), hypertension affected approximately 1.13 billion people worldwide, which was around 27% of the adult population. The WHO African Region has the highest prevalence of hypertension (27%), whereas the WHO Americas Region has the lowest incidence (18%). India is a young country and hypertension is the most important risk factor for death and disability in India. The prevalence of hypertension in India in the year 2013 is about 29.8% along with 27.6% and 33.8% prevalence of hypertension in rural and urban populations respectively (Anchala et al., 2014). The result from various studies in India by Ministry of Health and Family Welfare (MoHFW, 2016), have shown that urban areas have a prevalence of hypertension of 25% and rural has about 10%. The available evidence suggests prevalence of 13.9 to 46.3% in urban and 4.5 to 58.8% in rural areas of India; with overall prevalence at 29.8%. The 2019–2020 National Family Health Survey (NFHS-5) reported a hypertension prevalence of 24% in men and 21% among women, an increase from 19% and 17% respectively from the previous round (2015–16). According to the 2011 census, approximately 32% of its 1.2 billion population are young adults (aged 20-39 years). Assuming a prevalence of hypertension of around 7% among young adults (20-39 years of age), this amounts to around 27 million hypertensive young adults in India. It is well recognized that high blood pressure throughout adolescence promotes vascular damage, which leads to clinical events and mortality later in life. As per Department of Health and Family Welfare of Government of West Bengal, West Bengal has a 22% prevalence of hypertension and around one crore hypertensive persons. The state of West Bengal recorded nearly 25% of total annual deaths and 13% of disability adjusted life years (DALYs) attributed to hypertension.

According to Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC, 2023) and WHO (Hypertension, 2023), there are several risk factors that can contribute to the development of hypertension. Among those factors, modifiable risk factors include unhealthy diets, lack of physical activity, consumption of tobacco and excessive alcohol, and being

overweight or obese. Non-modifiable risk factors include a family history of hypertension; age over 65 years, certain medical conditions such as sleep apnea, hormonal disorders (e.g., Cushing's syndrome) and co-existing diseases such as diabetes or kidney disease.

The relation of hypertension (high blood pressure) with sleep duration is such that numerous studies have found that shorter sleep duration is associated with an increased risk of developing hypertension. Inadequate sleep, typically defined as less than 4-5 hours per night, has been linked to higher blood pressure levels and an elevated risk of hypertension (Grandner et al., 2018). While the focus is often on the effects of short sleep duration, some studies have also suggested a potential association between long sleep duration (typically defined as more than 8-9 hours per night) and hypertension (Grandner et al., 2018). The relationship between hypertension and sleep duration is bidirectional, meaning that each can influence the other (Hwang et al., 2015). On one hand, hypertension can disrupt sleep patterns, leading to difficulties falling asleep or staying asleep. The physiological effects of high blood pressure, such as increased sympathetic nervous system activity, can interfere with the normal sleep-wake cycle. On the other hand, inadequate sleep can contribute to the development or exacerbation of hypertension through various mechanisms, including increased inflammation, hormonal dysregulation, and altered cardiovascular function.

2. AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

Hypertension or High blood pressure is a medical condition characterized by elevated pressure in the arteries. According to the World Health Organization (WHO, 2023), hypertension affected approximately 1.13 billion people worldwide, which was around 27% of the adult population. India is a young country and hypertension is the most important risk factor for death and disability in India. The prevalence of hypertension in India in the year 2013 is about 29.8% along with 27.6% and 33.8% prevalence of hypertension in rural and urban populations respectively (Anchala et al., 2014). Since only a few studies were done on the association on sleep duration and hypertension in the age group of young adults, so a cross-sectional study was performed amongst the college students aged between 17 and 25 years to determine -

- 2.1 The prevalence of hypertension in association with socio-demographic, anthropometric and behavioral characteristics.
- 2.2 The prevalence of hypertension in association with socio-demographic, anthropometric and behavioral characteristics.
- 2.3 To establish the risk factors in developing hypertension in college youths.
- 2.4 To study the association between sleep duration and hypertension in normal college going individual.

3. LITERATURE REVIEW

Using a gender-specific, nationally representative adult population in the United States, Roka et al. (2015) have focused on the impact of anthropometric measurements, such as body mass index (BMI) and waist circumference (WC), on hypertension. The NHANES (National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey, 2009-2010) subsample comprised of 5886 persons of aged 21–80 years, was used in this study. This subsample was obtained through personal interviews, physical examinations, and laboratory tests. According to the data analyses that considered both genders, BMI in men and WC in women were both associated with greater risks of hypertension.

Recent epidemiological and clinical studies have shown that chronic ethanol consumption (more than three drinks per day, 30 g ethanol) is linked to an increased risk of cardiovascular illnesses and an increased incidence of hypertension. With participants ranging in age from 35 to 74 years old and of both sexes, a study conducted by (Santana et al., 2018) at six educational and research institutions throughout three different regions of Brazil to examine the relationship between alcohol consumption and high blood pressure among participants in the Brazilian Longitudinal Study of Adult Health (ELSA-Brasil). According to the study, males who drink moderately (OR = 1.69; 95% CI 1.35-2.11); and excessively (OR = 2.70; 95% CI 2.04-3.59) are more likely to have high blood pressure. After adjusting for the consumption of drinks with meals, binge drinkers who consume more than twice or three times per month have about a 70% greater chance of presenting with high blood pressure, and women have nearly a three times higher risk of presenting with high blood pressure when presenting excessive consumption (OR = 2.86, 95% CI 1.77-4.63).

Smoking and high blood pressure are known to be the two major risk factors for cardiovascular disease. Using information from the 2016 Nepal Demographic and Health Survey, which included a total of 5518 women and 3420 men with valid BP measurements, Lan et al. (2021) conducted a cross-sectional study to examine the differences in systolic blood pressure (SBP) and diastolic blood pressure (DBP) between current daily cigarette users and non-smokers in Nepali people aged 18 to 49 years. In this nationally representative study, it was found that daily cigarette smoking was not associated with higher blood pressure in either males or females in Nepal.

A community-based case control study was carried out by (Palal & Stalin, 2018) in the urban field practise area of a medical college in Puducherry, India, to determine the relationship between adult hypertension and mobile phone usage. A systematic questionnaire was used to interview fifty cases—those with an average blood pressure of 140/90 mmHg or higher—who had just been diagnosed with hypertension, and fifty controls—those with an average blood pressure of 130/85 mmHg or below. According to the study, the risk of hypertension was six times higher in people who had been using a mobile phone for more than 8 years and four times higher in people who made more than 60 minutes of calls every day. In conclusion, there was a significant positive association between hypertension

and the duration of mobile phone use.

Grandner et al. (2018) used a sizable, nationally representative dataset spanning 10 years to investigate the cross-sectional link between sleep duration and hypertension. Data were combined from the combined 2007–2016 National Health Interview Surveys ($n = 295,331$) and the 2013 Behavioral Risk Factor Surveillance System ($n = 433,386$). All analyses relied on combined surveys with survey-specific weights and self-reported history. In both surveys, the question, "On average, how many hours of sleep do you get in a 24-hour period?" was used to gauge the sleep duration. According to adjusted analyses, individuals who slept for ≤ 4 hours, 5 hours, 6 hours, 7 hours, 8 hours, 9 hours, and ≥ 10 hours showed an increased risk of hypertension. Their findings demonstrated that across the majority of age groups, both short and long sleep durations were linked to an elevated risk of hypertension. According to adjusted analyses and stratified sub-analyses, the relationship between short sleep and hypertension was found to be stronger and more dependable than the correlation between long sleep and hypertension. Furthermore, over the course of an adult's life, women's risk of hypertension was consistently stronger than men's. Also, analyzing the results of the longitudinal studies, it was found that short sleep length was significantly associated with hypertension, whereas extended sleep duration was not significantly associated with hypertension (Guo et al., 2013). In a study of 19,407 people between the ages of 18 and 79, Li et al. (2019) found that participants between the ages of 18 and 44 who slept less than 7 hours per day had a higher risk of hypertension than those who slept 7-8 hours per day. There were no statistically significant links between sleep duration and hypertension in the full sample of middle-aged people (45-59 years) and older adults (60-79 years). In contrast, a population-based cohort study by Lopez-Garcia et al. (2009) in Spain from 2001 to 2003 with 3,686 participants aged 60 or older discovered that, when compared to 7 hours of sleep, sleeping more or less was not significantly associated with prevalent hypertension in both genders. In conclusion, there was no correlation between the length of sleep and hypertension in older persons.

4. MATERIALS AND METHODS

4.1 Study area:

A study was performed in Kolkata and its adjoining areas of West Bengal which was conducted in Asutosh College, affiliated to the University of Calcutta in Kolkata, amongst the college students residing in different parts of West Bengal. The total area of West Bengal is 88,752 square km. As per the Census 2011, the total population of West Bengal is 9.13 Cr. Thus, the population of West Bengal forms 7.54 percent of India in 2011. West Bengal has total population of 91,276,115 in which males were 46,809,027 while females were 44,467,088.

4.2 Study design and Sampling Methodology:

This cross-sectional study was conducted using the data of 201 participants (students) of aged 17-25 years using convenient and voluntary response sampling method that comes under the divisions of non-probability sampling methodologies excluding the physically challenged students. Participants were interviewed using a structured interview schedule and the data were recorded for the further study. Participants were also informed that their identity, personal information, responses, etc. will not be disclosed to anyone outside the research team and their anonymity will be maintained.

4.3 Selection of Subjects:

Without considering any gender bias, college students of the age group between 17 years and 25 years were considered by their will and consent excluding the physically challenged and unfit students.

4.4 Tools used in the study:

A scheduled structured interview was carried out for acquiring data of the participants, comprised of 25 questions containing variables such as anthropometric factors, behavioral and non-behavioral risk factors and socio-demographic factors; Aneroid sphygmomanometer (AccuSure B07NC6HZ5Q) and Stethoscope (OMRON 416-22-BLK) for measuring BP, Pulse Oximeter (OMRON CMS50N) for measuring the pulse rate, digital weighing scale (OMRON HN 289), Stadiometer (PRESTIGE SM-P-W-210) and flexible and non-stretchable anthropometric tape (SECA) for measuring anthropometric factors such as Body Mass Index (BMI) and Waist-Hip ratios were used. The collected data were entered in MS Excel, and the data analysis was done using IBM SPSS Statistics (Version 26).

4.5 Blood Pressure (BP) Measurements:

According to the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC), Blood pressure is the pressure of blood pushing against the walls of your arteries. Blood pressure is measured using the aneroid sphygmomanometer following the guidelines of the "The Seventh Report of the Joint National Committee on Prevention, Detection, Evaluation, and Treatment of High Blood Pressure" (JNC 7, 2003).

Before measuring the BP, the participants' were asked to sit calmly with uncrossed legs for at least 5 minutes. The BP was then measured using a relevant cuff which was placed snugly around the bare and stretched out the upper arm, inflating it until no blood flowed through the brachial artery. Then the air is slowly let out of the cuff, allowing the pressure to slowly fall. The reading was then noted in the aneroid gauge by placing the stethoscope over the brachial artery of the bent elbow followed by the inflation and deflation of the cuff. As the pressure falls, the point at which the pounding sound of blood pulsing was first heard was recorded as the systolic blood pressure (SBP) of the participant. And, the points at which the sound stopped or disappeared were recorded as the diastolic blood

pressure (DBP) of the participant.

Classification of BP according to JNC-7:

- a. Normal:** Individuals with a systolic blood pressure less than 120 mmHg or a diastolic blood pressure less than 80 mmHg should be considered as normal.
- b. Pre-hypertension:** Individuals with a systolic blood pressure of 120–139 mmHg or a diastolic blood pressure of 80–89 mmHg should be considered as pre-hypertensive.
- c. Hypertension (High Blood Pressure):** Hypertension is a systolic blood pressure greater than 140 mmHg or a diastolic blood pressure greater than 90 mmHg.
- d. Stage 1 Hypertension:** Individuals with a systolic blood pressure of 140–159 mmHg or a diastolic blood pressure of 90–99 mmHg should be considered as stage 1 hypertensive.
- e. Stage 2 Hypertension:** Individuals with a systolic blood pressure greater than 160 mmHg or a diastolic blood pressure greater than 100 mmHg should be considered as stage 2 hypertensive.

4.6 Pulse rate Measurements:

By following the methodology according to the Harvard Medical School Special Health Report Diseases of the Heart (How to Monitor-and Lower-your Blood Pressure at Home - Harvard Health, 2013), the participants were asked to sit relax; and put their left hand forward with the palm facing upwards. Then the recorder lightly pressed the index and middle fingers on the inside of the participant's wrist, just below the base of the thumb to get the pulse point, between the bone and the tendon over the radial artery. The number of beats was counted for 15 seconds by using a timer and then multiplied by 4 to calculate the beats per minute. The number of beats per minute was recorded as the pulse rate of the participant.

4.7 Anthropometric Measurements:

To measure the anthropometric factors, the Anthropometry Procedures Manual of the National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey (NHANES) was followed.

4.8 Body Mass Index (BMI):

According to the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC, 2022) and World Health Organization (WHO, 2010), Body Mass Index (BMI) is a person's weight in kilograms (or pounds) divided by the square of height in meters (or feet). BMI is a simple index of weight- for- height that is commonly used for classifying overweight and obesity in adults.

For adults, WHO classifies BMI as follows:

- a) Underweight is a BMI lesser than 18.5
- b) Normal Range is a BMI which ranges between 18.5-24.9
- c) Overweight (pre-obese) is a BMI which ranges between 25-29.9
- d) Obesity or Obese is a BMI greater than or equal to 30. There are three classes of obesity-
 - i) Obese Class 1- BMI ranging between 30-34.9
 - ii) Obese Class 2- BMI ranging between 35-39.9
 - iii) Obese Class 3- BMI greater than or equal to 40.

4.9 Waist Circumference (WC) and Hip Circumference (HC):

Waist Circumference (WC) and Hip circumference (HC) are commonly assessed in guide measurements with flexible, but non-stretchable, tape in line with recommendations with the aid of the guidelines of WHO (2011) by wrapping the tape at the midpoint between the last rib and the iliac crest of the participant and at the level of the widest part of the hips, respectively, both in a horizontal plane for recording the WC and HC of the participant. For both measurements, participants were first asked to stand up straight with feet close together, arms at the side, and body weight evenly distributed and relaxed in order to measure the WC and HC of the individual.

4.10 Waist-Hip Ratio (WHR):

The WHR is the person's waist circumference (in centimeters) divided by the hip circumference (in centimeters).

4.11 Statistical Analysis:

The data obtained from the participants were collected in MS Excel first and then analyzed statistically using IBM SPSS Statistics (Version 26).

4.12 Ethical Clearance:

All procedures performed in studies involving human participants were in accordance with the ethical standards of the institutional ethical guideline and were approved by the Institutional Ethical Committee of Asutosh College, 92, Shyama Prasad Mukherjee Road, Bhowanipore, Kolkata - 700026.

5. DATA ANALYSES

For the entire study sample, behavioral characteristics and descriptive statistics for all variables were obtained. These analyses were performed using the sample weights that were provided. Pairwise comparisons utilizing chi-square tests were investigated for categorical variables.

Weighted binary and linear logistic regression analyses were performed to see if sleep duration was related to hypertension, with hypertension as the outcome and sleep duration as the predictor variable. Covariates in adjusted analyses were gender, obesity, abdominal obesity, smoking, alcohol, BMI, and income. These were computed individually for the combined sample and the research.

6. RESULT

The sample characteristics were summarized in **Table 1**. The majority of participants (N=201) were between the ages of 17 and 25 years with males (44.8%) and more than half were females (55.2%). With respect to education, the vast majority of participants are pursuing undergraduate program (80.6%) and few from postgraduate program (18.9%). Our data showed that 26.9% were below the official poverty threshold whereas 73.1% were above the poverty level. More than half of the participants (76.6%) were non-smokers. The proportion of participants who had hypertension was 4% and rest of the participants were normotensive (96%). The proportion of participants who were considered overweight and obese was 26.4% and 3.5%, respectively. Approximately 7.5% were considered abdominally obese according to their waist size. About more than half of the participants do not consume alcohol (71.6%), less than half consume alcohol regularly (21.9%), and a few occasionally (6.5%).

Table 1. Background Characteristics of the study subjects.

	<i>Variables</i>	<i>N (201)</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
<i>Sex</i>	<i>Male</i>	90	44.8
	<i>Female</i>	111	55.2
<i>Education</i>	<i>PG</i>	38	18.9
	<i>UG</i>	162	80.6
<i>Alcohol Consumption</i>	<i>No</i>	144	71.6
	<i>Occasional</i>	13	6.5
	<i>Regular Use</i>	44	21.9
<i>Smoking</i>	<i>Non-Smoker</i>	154	76.6
	<i>Smoker</i>	46	22.9

<i>Obesity</i>	<i>Normal</i>	141	70.1
	<i>Overweight</i>	53	26.4
	<i>Obese</i>	7	3.5
<i>Abdominal Obesity</i>	<i>Normal</i>	186	92.5
	<i>Abdominal Obesity</i>	15	7.5
<i>Hypertensive</i>	<i>Normotensive</i>	193	96.0
	<i>Hypertensive</i>	8	4.0
<i>Hypertension (HTN) Type</i>	<i>Normotensive</i>	193	96.0
	<i>Systolic HTN</i>	2	1.0
	<i>Diastolic HTN</i>	6	3.0
<i>Income Group</i>	<i>1000.1-16000.0</i>	54	26.9
	<i>16000.1-31000.0</i>	52	25.9
	<i>31000.1-46000.0</i>	35	17.4
	<i>46000.1-61000.0</i>	24	11.9
	<i>61000.1-76000.0</i>	12	6.0
	<i>76000.1+</i>	24	11.9

List of Figures showing the Background Characteristics of the study subjects:

Fig. 1: Percentage of male and female participants.

Fig. 2: Percentage of UG and PG students in the survey.

Fig. 3: Graph showing the percentage of participants who don't consume alcohol and consume alcohol on an occasional and regular basis.

Fig. 4: Graph showing the percentage of participants of non-smokers and smokers.

Fig. 5: Graph representing the percentage of normal, overweight, and obese participants in the survey.

Fig. 6: Graph showing participants with and without abdominal obesity in the survey.

Fig. 7: Percentage of normotensive and hypertensive participants.

Fig. 8: Graph showing participants with normotensive, systolic hypertension, diastolic hypertension.

Fig. 9: Percentage of participants with six categories of family income

General descriptive statistics of the studied participants were summarized in **Table 2**. The minimum and maximum Systolic BP were found to be 80 mmHg and 150 mmHg ($M = 107.58$, $SD = 11.422$). And, the minimum and maximum Diastolic BP were found to be 50 mmHg and 100 mmHg ($M = 72.31$, $SD = 8.845$). The calculated BMI was found to have minimum value of 156.56 kg/m^2 and a maximum value of 34.44 kg/m^2 ($M = 22.6735$ and $SD = 3.83303$). The minimum and maximum value of WHR was found to be 0.53 and 1.03 ($M = 0.7800$ and $SD = 0.06226$). The minimum and maximum age of the participants' were found to be 18 years and 24 years ($M = 20.263$ and $SD = 1.4254$). Family income of the participants' with a minimum income of Rs. 1,666 per month and a maximum income of Rs. 2,08,333 per month were recorded ($M = 36844.599$ and $SD = 31919.8278$).

Table 2. General descriptive statistics of the studied participants.

	<i>N</i>	<i>Minimum</i>	<i>Maximum</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Std. Deviation</i>
<i>SYS BP</i>	198	80	150	107.58	11.422
<i>DIA BP</i>	198	50	100	72.31	8.845
<i>BMI</i>	200	156.56	34.44	22.6735	3.83303
<i>WHR</i>	200	0.53	1.03	0.7800	0.06226
<i>Participant's Age</i>	201	18.0	24.0	20.263	1.4254
<i>Family Income per month</i>	201	1666.0	208333.0	36844.599	31919.8278

p-value was calculated using the chi-square test for all the parameters of all the participants were shown in **Table 3**. Considering sex of the participants, both males and females were found to have no significant relation with developing hypertension, $\chi^2 (1, N = 201) = 1.058, p = 0.304$. From the statistical analysis, obesity showed no significant association with hypertension in the participants, $\chi^2 (2, N = 201) = 2.189, p = 0.244$. In the participants, considering another parameter, i.e. abdominal obesity had showed no such significant relation with hypertension, $\chi^2 (1, N = 201) = 0.306, p = 0.580$. Also, there was no such association found between smoking and hypertension, $\chi^2 (1, N = 201) = 0.519, p = 0.471$ in the participants. From **Table 3**, it was found that alcohol consumption was not significantly associated with hypertension, $\chi^2 (2, N = 201) = 1.167, p = 0.558$. Since the value of *p* is non-significant, i.e. $p > 0.05$, there is no association between above mentioned parameters and hypertension. In contrast, family income of the participants showed a significant association with hypertension, $\chi^2 (5, N = 201) = 14.462, p = 0.013$.

Table 3. Normotensive and Hypertensive according to behavioral risk factors, anthropometric risk factors and socio-demographic characteristics.

<i>Variables</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>Normotensive</i>	<i>Hypertensive</i>	<i>Asymptotic significance</i>	
<i>Sex</i>	<i>Male</i>	90	85	5	$p = 0.304$
	<i>Female</i>	111	108	3	$df = 1$ $\chi^2 = 1.058$
<i>Obesity</i>	<i>Normal</i>	141	137	4	$p = 0.244$

	<i>Overweight</i>	53	50	3	df = 2
	<i>Obese</i>	7	6	1	$\chi^2 = 2.189$
<i>Abdominal</i>	<i>Normal</i>	186	179	7	$p = 0.580$
<i>Obesity</i>	<i>Abdominal</i>	15	14	1	df = 1
	<i>Obesity</i>				$\chi^2 = 0.306$
<i>Smoking</i>	<i>Non-Smoker</i>	154	147	7	$p = 0.471$
	<i>Smoker</i>	46	45	1	df = 1
					$\chi^2 = 0.519$
<i>Alcohol</i>	<i>No</i>	144	137	7	$p = 0.558$
	<i>Occasional</i>	13	13	0	df = 2
	<i>Regular Use</i>	44	43	1	$\chi^2 = 1.167$
<i>Exercise</i>	<i>No Exercise</i>	106	102	4	$p = 0.874$
	<i>Exercise</i>	95	91	4	df = 1
					$\chi^2 = 0.025$
<i>Income Group</i>	<i>1000.1-16000.0</i>	54	53	1	$p = 0.013$
	<i>16000.1-31000.0</i>	52	51	1	df = 5
	<i>31000.1-46000.0</i>	35	35	0	$\chi^2 = 14.462$
	<i>46000.1-61000.0</i>	24	20	4	
	<i>61000.1-76000.0</i>	12	12	0	
	<i>76000.1+</i>	24	22	2	

Binary logistic regression analyses and Odds Ratio (OR) from the overall model including all participants were

summarized in **Table 4**. From the **Table 4**, it was found that Obesity (1) was nearly associated with hypertension, (OR = 1.667, 95% CI [0.256, 10.862]) and Obesity (2) was also been found to be significantly associated with hypertension (OR = 70.056, 95% CI [0.678, 7237.812]). The statistical analysis also showed a negative association between sex of the individuals and hypertension (OR = 0.295, 95% CI [0.054, 1.613]). Also, taking reference from the table, consumption of alcohol and smoking in the age group between 17 to 25 years was found to have no association with hypertension (OR = 0.275, 95% CI [0.013, 5.596]) and (OR = 0.695, 95% CI [0.32, 15.022]). Family income of the participants' in Income group (3) was found to be significantly associated with hypertension (OR = 16.565, 95% CI [1.554, 176.584]) and Income group (5) was also found to be associated with hypertension (OR = 2.941, 95% CI [0.188, 45.901]). Since, the *p*-value of all the above parameters is greater than 0.05, therefore, their association with hypertension is not statistically significant except the family income of the participants.

Table 4. Logistic regression analysis for the association of hypertension and behavioral, anthropometric and socio-demographic factors.

	<i>df</i>	<i>p</i> -Value	Odds ratio	Class Interval (95%)	
				Lower	Upper
<i>Obesity</i>	2	0.199			
<i>Obesity (1)</i>	1	0.593	1.667	0.256	10.862
<i>Obesity (2)</i>	1	0.073	70.056	0.678	7237.812
<i>Sex(M-1/F-2) (1)</i>	1	0.159	0.295	0.054	1.613
<i>Alcohol</i>	2	0.713			
<i>Alcohol (1)</i>	1	0.998	0.000	0.000	.
<i>Alcohol (2)</i>	1	0.410	0.275	0.013	5.956
<i>Smoking (1)</i>	1	0.817	0.695	0.032	15.022
<i>Exercise (1)</i>	1	0.908	1.109	0.192	6.409
<i>UG/PG</i>	2	0.748			
<i>UG/PG (1)</i>	1	1.000	31465663.55	0.000	.
<i>UG/PG (2)</i>	1	1.000	14722390.24	0.000	.
<i>Income Group</i>	5	0.118			
<i>Income Group (1)</i>	1	0.768	0.624	0.027	14.269
<i>Income Group (2)</i>	1	0.997	0.000	0.000	.

<i>Income Group (3)</i>	1	0.020	16.565	1.554	176.584
<i>Income Group (4)</i>	1	0.999	0.000	0.000	.
<i>Income Group (5)</i>	1	0.442	2.941	0.188	45.901
<i>Abdominal Obesity</i>	1	0.397	0.180	0.003	9.450
<i>Constant</i>	1	1.000	0.000		

Binary and Linear Logistic regression analyses along with Odds Ratios (OR) from the overall model including all participants were summarized in Table 5. From the reference table, no association was found between sleep duration and hypertension in the age group of 17-25 years (OR = 0.998, 95% CI [0.992, 1.004]). It may or may not develop association with hypertension in future studies. Also, the use of mobile phone was found to be not associated with hypertension (OR = 1.002, 95% CI [0.932, 1.012]). Since, the *p*-value for sleep duration and mobile phone usage is found to be greater than 0.05, hence, these two parameters show no significant association with hypertension.

Table 5. Logistic regression analysis for the association of hypertension and sleep duration and mobile phone usage.

	<i>df</i>	<i>p-Value</i>	<i>Odds Ratio</i>	<i>Class Interval (95%)</i>	
				Lower	Upper

<i>Sleep Duration</i>	1	0.592	0.998	0.992	1.004
<i>(mins.)</i>					
<i>Mobile Phone Usage</i>	1	0.602	1.002	0.993	1.012
<i>(mins.)</i>					
<i>Constant</i>	1	0.051	0.056		

7. DISCUSSION

The current cross-sectional study was carried out at Asutosh College to investigate the relationship between anthropometric, behavioral, and socio-demographic characteristics and hypertension. A negative association between sex and hypertension was seen in the participants (N=201) aged between 17 and 25 years (OR = 0.295, 95% CI [0.054, 1.613]). Additionally, it was shown in the study that those who were overweight or obese had a higher risk of developing hypertension (OR= 1.667, 95% CI [0.256, 10.862]); (OR = 70.056, 95% CI [0.678, 7237.812]), but that there was no link between abdominal obesity and hypertension. Also, Participants who smoke and drink alcohol were found to have association between frequent alcohol intake and smoking and hypertension. Our findings for socio-demographic studies showed a positively significant relationship between monthly family income and hypertension (OR = 16.565, 95% CI [1.554, 176.584]); (OR = 2.941, 95% CI [0.188, 45.901]). There is no association observed between participants' education level and hypertension.

In this cross-sectional study, we observed no association between sleep duration and an increased risk of hypertension in young adults (17-25 years) (OR = 0.998, 95% CI [0.992, 1.004]). There have been several studies focusing on the relationship between sleep duration and high blood pressure. From the study of Grandner et al. (2018), their findings demonstrated that across the majority of age groups, both short and long sleep durations were linked to an elevated risk of hypertension for the individuals who slept for ≤ 4 hours, 5 hours, 6 hours, 7 hours, 8 hours, 9 hours, and ≥ 10 hours. According to adjusted analyses and stratified sub-analyses, the relationship between short sleep and hypertension was found to be stronger and more dependable than the correlation between long sleep and hypertension. Also, analyzing the results of the longitudinal studies, it was found that short sleep length was significantly associated with hypertension, whereas extended sleep duration was not significantly associated with hypertension (Guo et al., 2013).

In a study of 19,407 people between the ages of 18 and 79, Li et al. (2019) found that participants between the ages of 18 and 44 who slept less than 7 hours per day had a higher risk of hypertension than those who slept 7-8 hours per day. There were no statistically significant links between sleep duration and hypertension in the full sample of middle-aged people (45-59 years) and older adults (60-79 years). In contrast, a population-based cohort study by Lopez-Garcia et al. (2009) in Spain from 2001 to 2003 with 3,686 participants aged 60 or older discovered that, when

compared to 7 hours of sleep, sleeping more or less was not significantly associated with prevalent hypertension in both genders. In conclusion, there was no correlation between the length of sleep and hypertension in older persons. However, in our findings, no association between sleep duration and hypertension was observed as the limitation in this study lies in the properties of the cross-sectional study and the self-reported sleep duration. Also, the age group (17-25 years) criteria for the study do not provide supporting evidence for the association between sleep duration and hypertension.

8. CONCLUSION

In a sample of young college students, the findings of our study showed no correlation between sleep length and hypertension, showing that sleep duration is not a risk factor for hypertension in young adults.

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